

Recently released semidwarf rice variety Chaite 4 (IR9729-67-3), a cross of BG34-8/IR28//IR2095-625-1-252, and CH45, along with other test entries, were evaluated in multilocation trials in agricultural research stations and farmers' fields in the Tarai, inner Tarai, and river basin areas of the mid-hills Feb/Mar to Jun/Jul 1989.

Chaite 4 had a duration similar to that of CH45 in both the Tarai and the mid-hill regions. It produced an average 4.7 t/ha, 25% higher than CH45, with better yield performance at all sites (see table).

Chaite 4 has slender, medium-size grain with acceptable cooking and eating quality, is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and blast, and has longer grain dormancy than CH45. ■

Performance of Chaite 4 in on-station (Coordinated Varietal Trial) and on-farm trials at agricultural research stations, and farmers' field trial during 1989 Chaite dhan season.

Site	Tarai region (5 sites on-station ^a and 2 sites on-farm ^b)			Inner Tarai and river basin areas (2 sites on-station ^c and 4 sites on-farm ^d)			Mean			Yield increase (%) over CH45
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	
	<i>Chaite 4</i>									
On-station	4.5	122	82	4.0	153	78	4.4	132	81	22
On-farm	5.4	125	—	4.9	144	—	5.0	137	—	29
Mean	4.7	123	82	4.6	147	78	4.7	134	81	25
	<i>CH45</i>									
On-station	3.7	123	114	3.4	154	104	3.6	131	111	—
On-farm	3.4	130	—	4.2	139	—	3.9	136	—	—
Mean	3.6	125	114	3.9	144	104	3.7	133	111	—

^aKankai (altitude 90 m), Tarahara (100 m), Hardinath (93 m), Parwanipur (115 m), and Bhairahdwa (105 m) agricultural research stations. ^bJhapa (90 m) and Dhanusha (93 m). ^cGhorlekharka (600 m) area of Pakhribas Agriculture Center and Tapu (1000 m) area of Lumle Agriculture Center. ^d2 sites in Chitawan (256 m), Yampa Phant Tanahu (475 m), and Tapu (1000 m).

Jingmazhan, a high-yielding, good quality indica rice for China

Liao Changli, Ni Keyu, Liu Yuankun, and Huang Zonghong, Guizhou Academy of Agricultural Sciences (GAAS), Guiyang City, Guizhou, China

Jingmazhan, a new superlong, large-grain rice variety released in Guizhou Province, has been awarded the prize for high quality production by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture. ■

The variety was developed from (Reimei/Gui 630)B₃F₄//Zun 7201. Reimei is a japonica variety from Japan; Gui 630 and Zun 7201 are Guizhou native indica type cultivars. Jingmazhan is now planted in 35,000 ha.

Jingmazhan is 100 cm tall with 149-d duration, good plant type, and heavy tillering ability. Its 1,000-grain weight is 30.4 g and yield, 7.5 t/ha. Jingmazhan is moderately resistant to blast, sheath blight, cold temperature, and drought. ■

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, and cooking and eating quality meet the China National Index for high quality rice. Grain length is 7.5 mm, with 3:1 length-to-breadth ratio. Hulling recovery is 79.5%; milling recovery, 72.8%; and head rice recovery, 56.3%. Its grain is translucent, with 18.08% amylose, 8.0% protein content, low-gelatinization temperature (7.0 alkali spreading value), and medium gel consistency (60 mm). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Promising upland rice varieties for the North West Province of Cameroon

D. Janakiram, National Cereals Research and Extension Project (NCREP), B.P. 44; F. Jeutong, Institut de la Recherche Agronomique (IRA), B.P. 44, Dschang; M. P. Jones, NCREP; and J. A. Ayuk-Takem, IRA, B.P. 44, Dschang, Cameroon

Upland rice is cultivated as a subsistence food crop in areas with altitudes of 600-1200 m. Farmers tend to cultivate tall, low-tillering, upland varieties and, in some cases, irrigated varieties in the uplands. Trials at

Babungo (1150 m) and Befang (700 m) in the last 4 yr sought to identify adapted, high-yielding, disease-tolerant varieties with good grain quality.

Both sites have fertile and free-draining soils. Because of its higher altitude, Babungo has lower temperatures. Cultural practices at both sites were similar.

Performance of promising upland rice varieties in North West Cameroon.^a

Genotype	Babungo			Befang		
	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering (DAS)	Av yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering (DAS)	Av yield (t/ha)
IRAT109	74	108	3.8	75	89	4.1
IRAT112	76	102	3.8	80	80	3.8
M55 (check)	102	125	3.7	108	96	3.0
ITA208	86	123	3.5	88	94	4.3
ROK16	116	125	2.9	119	99	3.7

^aData averaged over 4 yr (1985-88). DAS = days after sowing.